

JRC Biomass Mandate

Wood availability, wood uses and forests in the EU

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Happy 25th Birthday!

EU Bioeconomy Strategy 2025

A Strategic Framework for a Competitive and Sustainable EU Bioeconomy

Scaling up innovation and investments: from lab to deployment

Developing lead markets for materials and technologies

Securing long-term prospects for the bioeconomy: sustainably sourced biomass

Harnessing global partnerships and opportunities

**Joining forces for delivery:
with Member States, industry, investors & civil society**

Assessment of EU biomass supply and demand

+6% since 2012

+11% since 2012

+14% since 2012

Camia A., Cazzaniga N., Tandetzki J., Magnolfi V., Gurría, P. (2025). *Biomass supply and demand in the EU 2012-2022*. JRC143910

EU BIOMASS SUPPLY IN 2022

Total 1.2 billion tons dry matter (Btdm), net imports 0.02 Btdm (1.8%)

PRIMARY SUPPLY

82% (990 Mtdm) of total (1.2 Btdm)

SECONDARY SUPPLY

7% (83 Mtdm) of total (1.2 Btdm)

TERTIARY SUPPLY

11% (127 Mtdm) of total (1.2 Btdm)

Unless otherwise specified, percentages are referred to the total of the category (% of primary or secondary or tertiary)

Trends in woody biomass uses for materials

	Sawnwood 		
Trends in production from 2010-2022	+ 13.3 %	+ 21.6 %	+ 3.2 %
Trends in apparent consumption from 2010-2022	+ 5.7 %	+ 12.6 %	- 4.1 %
Trade	the EU is a net exporter	the EU is a net exporter	the EU is a net importer

- Trends in production of sawnwood have increased the past decade by about 13%
- Trends in production of panels have increased the past decade by about 22%

Source: Cazzaniga et al. (Ch 3.2.3)
in EC-JRC et al. 2025

Unit: thousand cubic meters SWE
 Note: amounts smaller than 0.5 are not shown.

Lithuania, year 2021

Overview of EU forests

less than **3 %** of Europe's forests are primary and old-growth forests

more than **70 %** of European forests are even-aged

77 % of the forest area and **84 %** of the growing stock of European forests are available for wood supply

Source: Barredo et al. (Ch 3.2.1) in *EC-JRC et al. 2025*

Broadleaves and conifers in EU-27 forests

Broadleaves

Conifers

	Broadleaves	Conifers
Area in EU-27	47 %	53 %
Aboveground stock	16,000 Mm ³	20,000 Mm ³
Fellings to net annual increment (NAI) ratio	58-62 %	80-90 %
Trends in fellings to NAI ratio	Stable	Increasing
Wood provision	Provide about 70 % of the wood used as fuelwood	Provide about 80 % of the total industrial roundwood

Roundwood production has been, on average, **slightly above 500 Mm³ U.B.** the last 5 years of reporting

Source: Pilli et al. (Ch 3.2.2) in *EC-JRC et al. 2025*

Trends in the EU forest carbon sink

What is affecting the sink?

Long lasting

Controllable

Forest sink in 2070

- Between 2020 and 2030, when the total harvest is expected to increase by 0.6% per year, the biomass C sink is decreasing slightly
- After 2030, when harvest demand increases on average by 1.1% per year, while NAI is mostly stable, the living biomass sink rapidly decreases
- This is foreseen to only partially be counterbalanced by the HWP pool

Source: Rougieux et al. (Ch 4.2) in EC-JRC et al. 2025

Forest demand and supply in 2070

- Under the SSP2 economic pathway, harvest demand surpasses the available supply by 6% and 9%, in 2050 and 2070, respectively
- The differences between harvest expected and provided varies between countries

Regenerative actions

REGENERATING nature - through production methods that capture carbon and rebuild biodiversity, as well as returning nutrients to the soil.

Waste and Wastewater

e.g. sludges, bio-based waste

Products in **Lead Markets** (of today...and tomorrow)

Byproducts

Regeneration ambitions as part of the supply chain model

Bio-based plastics and polymers
Chemicals
Textile
Construction Products
Fertilisers and Pesticides

1%
In 2022

Biomass (raw materials)

Biomass Gap?

Secondary Biomass

Agriculture, forestry and fisheries

e.g. residues, manure, renure

Regenerative actions

5 Land and ecosystem-based management approaches

6 Sector-specific opportunities and challenges

6.1 Value added of biomass

Jesús Leizaola-López, Patricia Gurría, Francisco Javier Egeu González, Robert M'burak

The European Green Deal (EGD) has set ambitious targets to transform the European Union (EU) into a fair, resource-efficient, and competitive economy. This includes reaching zero net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, decoupling economic growth from resource use, and leaving no person or place behind. To achieve this, the EGD foresees actions in different areas, which are specified in a set of strategies and transversal instruments (European Commission, 2019). In this context, the sustainable management

Earth-centred land stewardship

Agroecology: strengthening the farmers' position

Sharing or sparing of forest land?

Nature-based climate solutions and carbon farming

Value added of biomass

Biomass and the European Bauhaus

Regenerative actions

Solutions

- Biodiversity-oriented afforestation
- Harvest reduction
- Increase rotation length
- Increase stand-age diversity
- Improve deadwood management
- Increase storage in harvested wood products

- Understanding the impact of climate extremes on forests
- Understanding the role of biodiversity as a climate-extreme buffer
- Quantification of climate extremes–harvest feedbacks
- Increasing forest resilience (age diversity and climate-resilient species)
- Assisted tree migration

Source: Migliavacca et al. 2025

Healthy ecosystems are the foundation of the EU Bioeconomy

EU-27 agroecosystems

24 %

of agroecosystems are in **good condition**

53 %

are **below a good condition threshold**

23 %
are in **bad condition**

Change in European* forest condition between 2000 and 2018

37 %
is the area showing **forest condition decline**

63 %

is the area showing **forest condition improvement**

*EU-27, UK, Switzerland, Norway, all Balkan countries, and partially Turkey

Importance of regenerative actions !

From 2003 to 2022, the share of EU-27 fish stocks considered to be within safe ecological limits grew by 150 %.

and the average biomass of assessed stock has consequentially increased

Concluding thoughts

Feasibility of the bioeconomy

what the EU needs to do for a successful bioeconomy strategy according to JRC evidence

1. **Deep understanding of biomass supply and demand**, the future development thereof and associated risks (environmental and geopolitical supply risks)
2. Strategies towards sustainable biomass should prioritize actions towards **regeneration of ecosystems** (to sustain current and future lead markets), **resource efficiency and ecodesign, circularity and cascading uses**
3. Bioeconomy is an umbrella strategy that interplays with different policies. **Policy coherence should be underpinned by solid scientific & technical coherence** and harmonisation along supply chains. This is key for *simplification*
4. Unlocking the **innovation for industrial transformation**. Assessing the potentials: scientific state of play, implementation in the industrial system state of play - where is the potential for bioeconomy solutions to operate at scale? Which indicators are supporting the industrial transition?

Sources used in this presentation

EU Biomass supply, uses, governance and regenerative actions

10-year anniversary edition

2025

Main source used in this talk

>60 authors from the Joint Research Centre, plus 14 universities and centres of excellence contributed!

European Commission, Joint Research Centre, EU Biomass supply, uses, governance and regenerative actions - 10-year anniversary edition, Mubareka, S.B. and Renner, A. (editors), Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/6511190>, JRC140117

Other sources used in this talk

1. European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Biomass production, supply, uses and flows in the European Union, Mubareka, S., Migliavacca, M. and Sanchez Lopez, J. editor(s), Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023
2. Camia, A., Cazzaniga, N., Tandetzki, J. et al. Biomass supply and demand in the EU 2012-2022, Korosuo, A., M'barek, R. and Camia, A. (editors), European Commission, Ispra, 2025, JRC143910.
3. Korosuo, A., Pilli, R., Abad Viñas, R. et al. The role of forests in the EU climate policy: are we on the right track? Carbon Balance Manage 18, 15 (2023).
4. Migliavacca, M., Grassi, G., Bastos, A. et al. Securing the forest carbon sink for the European Union's climate ambition. Nature 643, 1203–1213 (2025).
5. Mansuy, N., Barredo, J.I., Migliavacca, M et al. Reconciling the different uses and values of deadwood in the European Green Deal, One Earth, Volume 7, Issue 9, 2024, Pages 1542-1558.
6. Camia, A., Giuntoli, J., Jonsson, K. et al. The use of woody biomass for energy production in the EU, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2020, JRC122719.

JRC SCIENCE FOR POLICY REPORT

Biomass production, supply, uses and flows in the European Union

Integrated assessment

Abstract
The total supply of biomass in the EU summed up to 1.2 billion tons dry matter (DM) in 2022, with 82% coming from primary biomass, 7% from secondary biomass and 11% from recovered biomass.

Highlights

- The total supply of biomass in the EU summed up to 1.2 billion tons dry matter (DM) in 2022, with 82% coming from primary biomass, 7% from secondary biomass and 11% from recovered biomass.
- The main demand of biomass in the EU in 2022 was for food, feed and bedding (47% of the total known demand), followed by energy production (29%), and material production (24%).
- The overall EU biomass supply increased by 6% between 2012 and 2022. Demand for material and energy uses increased respectively by 11% and 14% over the same period.

Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy

We enhance the knowledge base for policymaking on the bioeconomy.

Carbon Balance and Management

RESEARCH

The role of forests in the EU climate policy: are we on the right track?

Abstract
The European Union (EU) has committed to achieving climate neutrality by 2050. This requires a rapid reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and ensuring that any remaining emissions are balanced through CO₂ removals. Forests play a crucial role in this plan as they are currently the main option for removing CO₂ from the atmosphere and additionally, wood use can store carbon durably and help reduce fossil emissions. To stop and reverse the decline of the forest carbon sink, the EU has recently revised the regulation on land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF) and set a target of +310 Mt CO₂e net removals for the LULUCF sector in 2030.

Results
In this study, we clarify the role of carbon concepts in forest management – net annual increment, harvest and mortality – in determining the forest sink. We then evaluate to what extent the forest sink is on track to meet the climate goal of the EU. For this assessment we use data from the latest national GHG inventories and a forest model (Forest Budget Model). Our findings indicate that on the EU level the recent decrease in increment and the increase in harvest and mortality are causing a rapid drop in the forest sink. Furthermore, continuing the past forest management practices is projected to further decrease the sink. Finally, we discuss options for enhancing the sink through forest management while taking into account adaptation and resilience.

Conclusions
Our findings show that the EU forest sink is quickly developing away from the EU climate targets. Step-

Perspective

Securing the forest carbon sink for the European Union's climate ambition

Abstract
The European Union (EU) climate policies rely on a functioning forest carbon sink. Forests cover about 40% of the EU area and have absorbed about 45 Mt of carbon dioxide equivalent per year between 1990 and 2022, which is about 20% of the EU's anthropogenic emissions. However, the ability of forests to act as carbon sinks is rapidly declining owing to increasing natural and anthropogenic pressures, threatening the EU's climate goal and calling for prompt actions. Here we provide actionable research recommendations to improve the monitoring and modelling of forest resources and their carbon sink, and to better inform forest management decisions. We suggest a number of actions that these measures to better support the implementation of strategies and policies outlined in the European Green Deal.

Perspective

Reconciling the different uses and values of deadwood in the European Green Deal

Abstract
The growing demand for woody biomass to meet the environmental and climate objectives of the European Green Deal raises concerns about the capacity of forest ecosystems to sustain their diverse services and functions. Deadwood, an often-overlooked source of biomass, exemplifies this dilemma, yet the evidence needed to enhance its management is sparse. Here, we put the role of deadwood into perspective through a literature review and comparison of estimates in managed and unmanaged forests. We demonstrate that deadwood interacts many overlapping and sometimes conflicting policies, playing a multifaceted role in the bioeconomy, biodiversity conservation, soil health, fire mitigation, biodiversity, and carbon storage. Given the increasing pressure on deadwood and the ecosystem services it provides, we argue that coherent and mutually supportive policies are needed to develop multifunctional pathways that reconcile deadwood management with biodiversity, bioeconomy, and climate objectives. Therefore, we suggest that harmonized data and monitoring are essential, along with transdisciplinary collaboration, to identify trade-offs between biomass uses and values and ensure the maintenance of functional forest ecosystems.

JRC SCIENCE FOR POLICY REPORT

The use of woody biomass for energy production in the EU

2020

Thank you!

JRC Biomass Mandate pages

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What is the sink?

Source: Korosuo et al, 2023

